

Complexes of Copper(II) with 2-Amino-5-nitrothiazole^ψ

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The magnetic and spectral properties of a number of complexes of 2-amino-5-nitrothiazole (ANT) with copper(II) are reported. On the basis of results presented here and evidence obtained previously, it is suggested that the copper acetate complex of ANT is dimeric: $[\text{Cu}(\text{AcO})_2(\text{ANT})]_2$, with a structure resembling that of copper acetate monohydrate. The compound $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{ANT})_2$ is thought to be five-coordinate and $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{ANT})(\text{DMF})$ is suggested to be a six-coordinate polymer with halogen bonding. $\text{CuCl}_4(\text{HANT})_2$ contains a protonated ligand and is probably of the type A_2CuCl_4 .

Metal complexes of 2-aminonitrothiazole (ANT) have been described in a previous paper¹. In this communication we report the magnetic properties and some further spectral data for some copper complexes.

Results and Discussion

Magnetic measurements: The effective magnetic moments were calculated using the expression,

$$\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.84\sqrt{\chi_m T}$$

where χ_m is the molar susceptibility corrected for TIP and $N_A = 60 \times 10^{-6}$ c.g.s.u.

The results (Tables 1–5) indicated antiferromagnetic interaction in all complexes, with the exception of $\text{CuCl}_4(\text{HANT})$; a subnormal magnetic moment was shown by $[\text{Cu}(\text{AcO})_2(\text{ANT})]_2$.

Spectra: Infrared spectral data have been reported previously¹, where we concluded that $[\text{Cu}(\text{AcO})_2(\text{ANT})]_2$ and $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{ANT})_2$ contain ring bonded ANT, whereas $\text{CuSO}_4(\text{ANT})(\text{DMF})$ and $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{ANT})(\text{DMF})$ have amine bonded ANT.

Diffuse reflectance spectra of the compounds showed bands as follows: $[\text{Cu}(\text{AcO})_2(\text{ANT})]_2$, 13 900 cm^{-1} ; $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{ANT})_2$, 13 500 cm^{-1} ; $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{ANT})(\text{DMF})$, 14 200 cm^{-1} ; $\text{CuSO}_4(\text{ANT})(\text{DMF})$, 11 000 cm^{-1} ; and $\text{CuCl}_4(\text{HANT})_2$, 13 000 cm^{-1} .

$[\text{Cu}(\text{AcO})_2(\text{ANT})]_2$: The magnetic data, infrared and electronic spectra are consistent with the

formulation of a dimer, thus the dimeric nature of copper acetate monohydrate, $[\text{Cu}(\text{AcO})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]_2^{2-5}$ is retained in the ANT complex. The observed magnetic moment in the hydrate is 1.4 B.M. and the Cu–Cu distance is 2.64 Å³.

TABLE 1—EXPERIMENTAL VALUES OF THE FIELD INDEPENDENT SUSCEPTIBILITY OF $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{ANT})_2$

Diamagnetic correction = 174.36×10^{-6} c.g.s.u.
 $\nu = -13$ K (susceptibilities given in c.g.s.u.)

T K	$\chi_m \times 10^6$	$1/\chi_m$	μ_{eff} B.M.
323.2	1 493.32	669.65	1.93
299.2	1 593.45	627.57	1.92
283.2	1 674.66	597.14	1.92
263.2	1 782.26	561.09	1.91
243.2	1 917.31	521.56	1.91
223.2	2 071.31	482.79	1.90
203.2	2 271.15	440.30	1.90
183.2	2 509.83	398.43	1.90
163.2	2 801.33	356.97	1.90
143.2	3 122.72	320.23	1.88
123.2	3 541.24	282.39	1.86
103.2	4 176.15	239.46	1.85
91.2	4 671.91	214.05	1.84

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The influence of the *trans*-axial ligands (where the water molecule in copper(II) acetate monohydrate is replaced by another ligand) on the Cu-Cu bond in dimeric acetates has been the subject of numerous investigations⁶⁻¹⁰. The differences in observed magnetic moments and spectral bands have been explained in terms of σ -donation and π -acceptance, and the basicities of the axial ligands. The magnetic moments of the adducts decrease slightly with the basicity of the *trans*-axial ligands. The greatest decrease in moments is reported for complexes capable of π -backbonding such as triphenylphosphine, pyrazine and 4-nitropyridine-*N*-oxide. Higher moments are reported where no π -bonding is possible, for example, the aniline adduct of copper(II) butyrate has a moment of 1.75 B.M. but still retains the dimeric structure of copper butyrate⁹.

TABLE 2—EXPERIMENTAL VALUES OF THE FIELD INDEPENDENT SUSCEPTIBILITY OF $\text{CuSO}_4(\text{ANT})(\text{DMF})$

Diamagnetic correction = 155.8×10^{-6} c.g.s.u.
 $\nu = 30$ K (susceptibilities given in c.g.s.u.)

<i>T</i> K	$\chi_m \times 10^6$	$1/\chi_m$	μ_{eff} B.M.
343.2	1 466.22	682.03	1.97
299.2	1 652.95	604.98	1.96
283.2	1 746.32	572.63	1.96
243.2	2 026.42	493.48	1.96
223.2	2 166.16	461.65	1.95
203.2	2 353.20	424.95	1.94
163.2	2 913.40	343.24	1.94
143.2	3 251.86	307.52	1.93
123.2	3 660.33	273.20	1.89
103.2	4 162.18	240.26	1.85
91.2	4 594.00	217.68	1.83

In $[\text{Cu}(\text{AcO})_2(\text{ANT})]_2$ the retention of dimeric structure is supported by the following observations: (a) the infrared spectrum exhibits the carboxylate stretching frequencies, νCO_2 -(sym) and νCO_2 -(assym) at 1 645 and 1 413 cm^{-1} respectively, at similar positions to those in the acetate monohydrate¹¹; (b) the magnetic moment of 1.38 B.M. suggests coupling of the copper atoms; (c) the variation of χ_{Cu} with temperature resembles that reported for copper(II) acetate monohydrate and substituted pyridine adducts⁹.

The copper acetate complex of 2-aminothiazole, $\text{Cu}(\text{AcO})_2(\text{AMT})$ has been assigned a polymeric octahedral structure¹². However, the reported room temperature moment of 1.61 B.M. casts some doubt on this structural assignment, and the complex is probably dimeric. However, the higher magnetic moment (1.61 B.M.) than that of the ANT complex (1.38 B.M.) may reflect bonding to the copper by the amine nitrogen rather than by the ring nitrogen as in the nitro-substituted ANT, emphasising the importance of subtle differences between these two ligands. Pyridine coordinates to transition metal ions both more frequently and more strongly than aromatic amines, for whereas aniline can form only a classical dative link to the metal, pyridine can potentially form a multiple bond through participation of a quinoid-type structure. Thus, the differences in the moments of 2-aminothiazole and ANT adducts of copper(II) acetate could be the result of the ability of ring-nitrogen-coordinated ANT to take part in metal-ligand bonding. This would provide a mechanism by which an excessive accumulation of negative charge on the metal from the σ -bond could be, in part, alleviated by means of the π -bond of the reverse polarity. In the case of 2-aminothiazole, if coordination is through NH_2 as in aniline, no such mechanism can exist, giving rise to the higher moment.

TABLE 3—EXPERIMENTAL VALUES OF THE FIELD INDEPENDENT SUSCEPTIBILITY OF $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{ANT})(\text{DMF})$

Diamagnetic correction = 165.8×10^{-6} c.g.s.u.
 $\nu = -10$ K (susceptibilities given in c.g.s.u.)

<i>T</i> K	$\chi_m \times 10^6$	$1/\chi_m$	μ_{eff} B.M.
299.2	1 509.84	662.32	1.87
263.2	1 708.08	585.45	1.87
203.2	2 190.95	456.42	1.87
183.2	2 397.38	417.12	1.86
163.2	2 660.18	375.91	1.85
143.2	2 956.65	301.67	1.83
123.2	3 427.69	291.74	1.83
103.2	4 056.94	246.49	1.81
91.2	4 478.60	223.28	1.80

However, the above argument does not eliminate the possibility of ring nitrogen bonded 2-aminothiazole, because the electron charge density

on the ring nitrogen may be of even more importance, and the difference in the magnetic moments could be a consequence of the ' π -deficient' character of ANT, in that the nitro group attracts electrons from the π -layer of the ring. In contrast, in 2-aminothiazole the lone-pair of NH_2 is released to the π -layer of the ring, thereby making it ' π -excessive', and lowering its capacity to form a strong coordinate link to copper. Therefore, although the coordination site in 2-aminothiazole is not clear because of insufficient data on this complex, the coordination of ANT in $[\text{Cu}(\text{AcO})_2(\text{ANT})]_2$ is most probably through the ring nitrogen, in agreement with the infrared data¹.

TABLE 4—EXPERIMENTAL VALUES OF THE FIELD INDEPENDENT SUSCEPTIBILITY OF $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{HANT})_2$

Diamagnetic correction = 227.02×10^{-6} c.g.s.u
 $\nu = 0$ (susceptibilities given in c.g.s.u)

T K	$\chi_m \times 10^6$	$1/\chi_m$	μ_{eff} B.M.
299.2	1 517.10	659.15	1.87
263.2	1 726.46	579.22	1.88
223.2	2 033.52	491.76	1.88
163.2	2 747.67	363.94	1.88
143.2	3 103.58	322.21	1.87
123.2	3 626.97	275.71	1.88
93.2	4 759.84	210.09	1.88

$\text{CuCl}_2(\text{ANT})_2$: The magnetic moment of $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{ANT})_2$ is 1.96 B.M. and is in the range reported for five-coordinate Cu^{II} ions (1.7–2.2 B.M.). The Weiss constant $\theta = -13$ K (Table 1) is smaller than the reported values for linear chain pyridine series, and it is even smaller than the Weiss constant for the dimeric $\text{CuCl}_2(2\text{-methylpyridine})_2$ complex (-17 K)¹³. Thus any interaction between the metal ions in the ANT complex must be quite small.

From X -ray powder diffraction measurements on powders, $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{ANT})_2$ has the same structure as $\text{CoCl}_2(\text{ANT})_2$, and we have suggested that both compounds are five-coordinate¹ with the thiazole ring bonded through the ring nitrogen. The esr spectrum of powdered $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{ANT})_2$ ¹⁴ is not inconsistent with this geometry : three rhombic g values were observed with $g_1 = 2.054$, $g_2 = 2.131$, $g_3 = 2.205$. The reflectance spectrum shows a broad band centred at $13\,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Reflectance spectra of

Cu^{II} complexes are generally poor indicators of geometry; however, it has been suggested^{8,15} that *tbp* Cu^{II} will absorb in the range $11\,800\text{--}12\,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$, whereas *spy* Cu^{II} will absorb between $14\,500$ and $18\,200\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and complexes having intermediate geometries will absorb at intermediate values.

TABLE 5—EXPERIMENTAL VALUES OF THE FIELD INDEPENDENT SUSCEPTIBILITY OF $[\text{Cu}(\text{AcO})_2(\text{ANT})]_2$

Diamagnetic correction = 123×10^{-6} c.g.s.u

T K	$\chi_m \times 10^6$	$1/\chi_m$	μ_{eff} B.M.
296.0	863.43	115.82	1.38
263.0	908.58	110.06	1.34
220.1	822.36	121.60	1.16
196.7	745.35	134.17	1.04
164.3	644.63	155.13	0.88
140.1	537.24	186.14	0.73
99.0	372.85	268.20	0.50
85.2	326.62	306.17	0.43

Thus $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{ANT})_2$ appears likely to be five-coordinate with halide bridges of the type found in bis[dibromobis(4-methylthiazole)copper(II)]¹⁶. The structure of $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{ANT})_2$ is thus intermediate between those of the thiazole complex, $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{thiazole})_2$ and the 2-aminothiazole complex, $\text{CuCl}_2(2\text{-aminothiazole})_2$ which have infinite of halogen bridged chains, with *trans*-thiazole ligands^{17,18}; and that of the *trans*-[dichlorobis(2,4-dimethylthiazole)copper(II)] which is square-planar and monomeric¹⁹. An alternative structure would be an elongated rhombic octahedron as postulated for $\text{NiCl}_2(\text{ANT})_2$ ¹. However, the copper and nickel compounds are not isomorphous.

$\text{CuCl}_2(\text{ANT})(\text{DMF})$: The most likely structure for $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{ANT})(\text{DMF})$ is halogen bridged octahedral, with amine bonded N. The position and the shape of the broad band in the reflectance spectrum at $14\,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is similar to the band observed in the spectrum of $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{thiazole})_2$ and $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{pyridine})_2$ which have halogen bridged octahedral geometry¹⁸. The magnetic moment measurement results indicated the antiferromagnetic nature of the ANT complex with $\nu = -10$ K. The value of ν for $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{ANT})(\text{DMF})$ is less than the corresponding value for the pyridine analogue¹³, indicating longer Cu–Cu distances.

$\text{CuSO}_4(\text{ANT})(\text{DMF})$: Four bands in the infrared spectrum at 995, 1 065, 1 133 and 1 170 cm^{-1} indicate a C_{2v} symmetry for the sulphate ion, thus indicating that the sulphate is bidentate or bridging. The position of the broad, featureless band at 1 100 cm^{-1} in the reflectance spectrum would favour tetrahedral, rather than square-planar geometry which usually absorb at higher energies. The magnetic susceptibility data give $\nu = 30$ K, indicating an antiferromagnetic exchange which apparently is propagated through-space via O-O interactions in the O-S-O moieties of a sulphate bridge. Thus there is at present no clear evidence as to the structure of this compound.

$\text{CuCl}_4(\text{HANT})_2$: When concentrated HCl was added slowly to either $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{ANT})(\text{DMF})$ or $\text{CuSO}_4(\text{ANT})(\text{DMF})$ small shining green crystals of $\text{CuCl}_4(\text{HANT})_2$ were formed. Comparison of the infrared spectra of ANT, $\text{HANT}^+(\text{ANT.HCl})$ and $\text{CuCl}_4(\text{HANT})_2$ clearly suggests that this compound contains the HANT^+ unit. However, the infrared spectrum of ANT.HCl does not distinguish between protonation at the ring-N or at the NH_2 group. The band at 3 220 cm^{-1} falls within the range associated with primary amine stretching, while the band at 1 595 cm^{-1} is typical of NH_3^+ . There are also bands at 1 635 and 1 648 cm^{-1} . Although it has been suggested that in solution ANT is protonated on the ring nitrogen, it seems likely that in the solid state a hydrogen bonded system occurs. The bands associated with HANT^+ are all present in the infrared spectrum of the complex, with small negative shifts in frequencies of the bands corresponding to νNH_2 and ring stretching vibrations.

The reflectance spectrum of $\text{CuCl}_4(\text{HANT})_2$ shows a broad band centred at 13 000 cm^{-1} . Compounds of the type A_2CuCl_4 generally contain either a tetragonally elongated CuCl_6 chromophore or a distorted tetrahedral CuCl_4^{2-} ion. The best example of square-coplanar CuCl_4^{2-} is $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{CuCl}_4$. The diffuse reflectance spectrum of this compound²⁰ shows three $d-d$ bands in the range 10 000 – 15 000 cm^{-1} . The crystal spectrum at 77 K of $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)_2\text{CuCl}_4$ which contains the CuCl_6 tetragonal chromophore, exhibits three bands in the range 10 000–14 000 cm^{-1} ²¹. The diffuse reflectance spectra of several tetrachlorocuprates(II) containing the CuCl_6 tetragonal group show a broad band at about 23 000 cm^{-1} with a shoulder at

10 000 – 11 000 cm^{-1} ²². A number of compounds of the type A_2CuCl_4 containing discrete CuCl_4^{2-} ions, which are flattened tetrahedra, have been studied by means of their electronic spectra^{23,24}. Cs_2CuCl_4 , $(\text{NMe}_4)_2\text{CuCl}_4$ and bis(trimethylbenzylammonium)-tetrachlorocuprate(II) show bands at about 9 000, 6 000 and 4 000 cm^{-1} in their polarised crystal spectra. Thus the position of the $d-d$ transition band at 13 000 cm^{-1} is in the range associated with tetragonally elongated CuCl_6 chromophores. Moreover, the charge transfer band observed in the spectra of CuCl_6 chromophores, such as $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3)_2\text{CuCl}_4$, $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_3)_2\text{CuCl}_4$ ^{24,26,29}, between 24 000 and 25 000 cm^{-1} , also appears in the spectrum of $\text{CuCl}_4(\text{HANT})_2$. Another factor supporting this assignment is the fact that hydrogen bonding in the $\text{Cu}(\text{A})_2\text{Cl}_4$ group favours the formation of square-coplanar CuCl_4^{2-} rather than tetrahedral CuCl_4^{2-} ion. The magnetic susceptibility studies showed that the magnetic moment of this compound is almost constant over a large temperature range, at 1.87 ± 0.02 B.M., and is very close to the room temperature moments observed for CuA_2Cl_4 compounds²⁵. No antiferromagnetic interaction was detected, most probably because of the size of HANT which would screen the adjacent copper(II) ions.

Experimental

The preparation and analyses of the following compounds have been reported¹ : $\text{CuCl}_2(\text{ANT})_2$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{AcO})_2(\text{ANT})]_2$, $\text{CuSO}_4(\text{ANT})(\text{DMF})$, $\text{CuCl}_4(\text{HANT})$. ANT.HCl was prepared by the slow addition of ANT to mechanically concentrated HCl until a white precipitate formed. Stirring was continued for 1h. The compound was dried and stored in a vacuum desiccator. Magnetic and spectroscopic measurements on the compounds were carried out as before¹.

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